

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers:

This is a new record ... although a slightly negative one: this issue consists of a single paper: "On the Power of Membrane Computing" by Jürgen Dassow and Gheorghe Paun. However, less is often more: it is a truly excellent paper. The other good news is, the March issue (a special issue on *Integration of Deduction Systems*) is already under preparation, and we also seem to be collecting quite a few contributions for April. Nevertheless: don't forget to send us good contributions, and encourage your colleagues to do so as well!

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
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